

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Sylvain**FIRST NAME:** Nzohabonayo**PROGRAM CODE:** DSDD**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 6-14)
2. Punctuation (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 15-23)
3. American versus British English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 33-39)
5. Style guide and Chicago Manual of Style (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 40-57)
6. Latin abbreviation and expression (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 58-64)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

After reading and interacting with the content of this course, I realised that academic writing has rules which are useful in guiding and harmonizing research work. This response paper is a period one paper written in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the course ACA-401/ACA-401D-International Academic Writing. At the end of this course, I intend to refresh the knowledge I have and gain more insights. Apart from the fact that I want to perform well in it, my main objective is to develop research skills and be of help to the academic world, which undoubtedly ends up enlightening the actions of leaders in enhancing the socioeconomic development of countries through practice that is well informed by research. The content of this paper is made of discussions on my critical interaction with key concepts of the period one lesson: essay writing, punctuation, American versus British English, plagiarism, style guide and Chicago Manual of Style, and Latin abbreviation and expression.

2) **BODY**

As mentioned above, the next paragraphs of this paper, I discuss my understanding and arguments on concepts like: essay writing, punctuation, American versus British English, plagiarism, style guide and Chicago Manual of Style, and Latin abbreviation and expression.

a) Essay Writing

Since it is easy to get lost in a way that is strange to someone unless he or she is guided, it is of great importance to take this lesson on essay writing in order to know the basics, steps and rules that are followed in an academic writing. As stated by Cleenewerck & Gulma (2021, 7), “Academic essays seek to provide answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence.” In his or her undertaking, I understood that the writer must have an aim and objective he or she wants to attain. That is the reason why learning from other academic authorities in a given field is very important to avoid duplicating the work or reinvesting means in what has already been done successfully. I conquer with the authors of this course, an academic writing needs to be done to bring in tangible contributions to the already existing knowledge. Brainly (2023) emphasizes that every research project should make a contribution to the researcher’s development in terms of finances, knowledge and/or in terms of methodology.

For the above to be achieved, an academic writing calls for proper planning. Pasha, Poister and L.H. Edwards (2015) state that planning is

A rational-comprehensive approach to strategy formulation that uses a systematic process with specific steps such as external and internal assessments, goal setting, analysis, evaluation and action planning to ensure long-term vitality and effectiveness of the organization (5).

The student understands that the writing of an academic paper needs proper planning, to be prepared to have a content, which is capable to substantially withstand competition with others produced in the same field and even to be presented in a format that makes it marketable. Ancestors used to say that a quality product attracts its own buyers. As I learnt in life, any word or text that goes out of the mouth needs to be verified. For that reason, and as recommended by Turabian (2018), the proofreading of a research paper by an editor and considering constructive comments is very important (125).

b) Punctuation

Cleenewerck & Gulma (2021, 16) recommend writers to use little punctuation to retain the meaning of the sentence. According to Eman Abdulsalam Al-Khalil (2022),

Punctuation is a system of symbols or signs used to separate sentences or clauses to make the meaning clear, to show readers where sentences start and end, and whether used

properly to make writing effective, comprehensive, and understandable. Punctuation is critical to good communication; it becomes confusing and tricky when misused (78).

From the observations above and recommendations, it is clear that the misuse of punctuation jeopardises the sentence's meaning. What I have already seen in some instances, mistakes made in punctuation lead to miserable situations. For example, I find a big difference between “Do not let him go habits kill” and “Do not let him go habits, kill.” In my understanding, “Do not let him go habits kill” means that the habits of do not let him go can kill, while “Do not let him go habits, kill” gives an order to kill. I indeed used to be very careful, but now, I will have to be vigilant in handling punctuation marks in my texts.

c) American Versus British English

To avoid confusion, I understand that the choice of English to be used, whether the Standard British or Standard American English, needs to be consistent. In my observations, I realized that the American English appears to be too dynamic and sometimes using slang or jargons. It calls for more efforts to keep the updates of the Standard American English. I am still struggling to have the two versions separate in my mind. This course has been and will still be of great help to me.

d) Plagiarism

According to Cleenerck & Gulma (2021, 34), “Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.” Even though one may think that he or she did plagiarism by ignorance, Turabian (2018) warns writers that,

The problem is that we read words, not minds. So think of plagiarism not as an intended act but as a perceived one. Here is the best way to think about this: If the author of the source you borrowed from were to read your paper, would she recognize any of it as hers, including paraphrases and summaries, or even general ideas or methods from her original work? If so, you must cite those borrowings (83).

In my understanding, beside the fact that plagiarism is an academic offense, it is also theft, dishonesty and lack of respect to the author of the work used. I find plagiarism to be an act that, if allowed or not perceived, compromises the tracking of the evolution of research in the concerned field because what one has brought as new contribution to the existing knowledge needs to come out clearly, to have a clearcut of what is already known and what is yet to be known and that should constitute the basis and recommendation for further studies.

e) Style Guide and Chicago Manual of Style

Children are being born today, but there are other people who die and who have been there before us. Those who have been there have information or knowledge that is

unknow to us unless we find it in written documents or unless it is said to us by those who lived it. For this reason, I cannot learn of a story and tell it as fresh without citing its source on an incident or event which took place when I was not there. Honesty, which is the basis of accountability compels me to recognize the author of the information that I use because it helps me as it will also help others. Since EUCLID accepts any form of referencing if it remains consistent from the beginning to the end of the paper (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 11), I will use the recent Chicago Manual of Style of the Modern Language Association (MLA) style (Turabian 2018).

f) Latin Abbreviations and Expressions

I grew up with a feeling that Latin abbreviations and expressions are good in sound and for shortening a writing. However, I ended up realizing that they are understood by those who know them whether they are acronyms, initialisms or contractions as distinguished in the Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations (Turabian 2018, 343). To those who do not know them, I keep in mind that abbreviations need to be added in parentheses after the full statement of what they stand for, when allowed and needed (*eadem*), to help readers know and understand the content. This is helpful not only to those who do not know them but also because they sometimes look alike meaning different things. In the same line of ideas, I agree with (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 59) who recommend that “It is best to create content using ‘plain language’ principles.”

3) CONCLUSION

To compare, to verify and check whether an academic paper meets the requirements and standard, International Academic Writing rules are needed to guide both the writer and the evaluator. Apart from the objectives pursued by the writer, these rules help the evaluator to be objective and fair when analysing and grading academic papers. In my understanding, it is objective and fair to evaluate or compare papers when they have been written guided by the same measures and rules. Since an academic publication comes to inform and add value to the existing knowledge as already seen above, the importance of International Academic Writing rules is paramount in that it helps researchers and students from all over the world read, learn and understand clearly the content of an academic paper in a format that does not confuse them and which also helps them understand and compare it to others. In my interaction with the content of this course, I discovered that its key concepts address issues, which lead to research development and facilitate healthy competition in academic writing. At the end of this response paper one, I am determined to continue revising this course and consider it to be a-day-to-day tool I need to have throughout this program and further academic work I will do in life.

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